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ORGANIZATION OF THE SIMULATION TRAINING IN THE CARDIOPULMONARY RESUSCITATION WITHIN THE STUDENT SCIENTIFIC GROUP OF THE DEPARTMENT OF THE DISASTER MEDICINE DURING THE PANDEMIC OF THE CORONAVIRUS INFECTION

Loginova S.,

Pirogov Russian National Research Medical University,

Kovaleva E.,

Pirogov Russian National Research Medical University,

Muradova M.,

Pirogov Russian National Research Medical University,

Kostyuchenko M.

Pirogov Russian National Research Medical University, Doctor of medical sciences

ABSTRACT

The article presents analysis of the students training of the basic cardiopulmonary resuscitation in the medical universities during anti-epidemic regime-restrictive measures for prevention of spreading of the coronavirus infection from 2019 to 2022.

Cardiopulmonary resuscitation is one of the most useful and important skill in the practice of any medical worker. Also, it is important to properly organize the studying process in the medical universities. So in the standard education program students do not always have the possibility to study the peculiarities of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation and sometimes they cannot master its technic. During the pandemic of the coronavirus infection to follow the anti-epidemic regime- restrictive measures students were studying in the distance learning format and did not have the possibility to visit the simulation studying centers and the practical classes. That's why it was urgent to develop new platform for rapid active acquisition of the practical skills of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation by students.

The student scientific group is an important aspect for the future specialization because it gives the first knowledge about the chosen profession and the ability to develop the skills which are useful to the future work. Therefore, the object of studying during the weakening of the quarantine measures was the opening of the practical sessions in the student scientific group meetings and the ability to study the cardiopulmonary resuscitation there.

Keywords: SSG, CPR, session, student, skills.

Aim: study of the work organization of the student scientific group of the disaster medicine; indicate its contribution to the process of student studying; consider the features of learning the algorithm of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation by the students of the medical universities in the student scientific group meetings.

Materials and methods: an analysis of a work of the student scientific group was made during the anti-epidemic regime-restrictive measures for prevention of the spreading of the coronavirus infection from 2019 to 2022; the peculiarities of the organization of the theoretical and practical meetings, which were dedicated to

study the technique of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation, were considered.

Results: In 2019 the new coronavirus infection appeared in the world. The first cases were registered in autumn in Wuhan (China). During the two-three months the wave of the coronavirus infection was spread all over the world (picture 1). This forced the medical service to act urgently to prevent further spreading of highly contagious disease with high mortality rate and poorly responding for treatment.

Picture 1.

The graph of spreading of coronavirus infection from 28 January 2020 year to 25 August 2022 year. [1]

For prevention of spreading of coronavirus infection in Russia from 30 March to 11 May 2020 there was a quarantine with the transfer of all educational institutions, including medical universities, to distance learning format. Students of the middle course, who passed the exam to work as a nurse, have been working in this position during the COVID-2019 pandemic; students of the first, second and third courses were voluntarily recruited as volunteers, nurses or have been practicing in the university clinics during pandemics. There was the full distant format of learning in the Pirogov Russian National Research Medical University (Pirogov Medical University) until the 1 February 2021 year. As information about the disease was accumulated, as there was the studying and analysis of the possible treatment, the development of the vaccine and the improvement of the epidemiological situation students could have practical lessons in the university from February to June 2021 year but there were a lot of cases when the students groups were quarantined due to identified cases of the disease. The epidemic situation was stabilized only by the end of the 2021 year when students were almost allowed to full studying in the university. During the distance learning students could not practice skills of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) with the usage of the simulation equipment. That's why there was an urgent need to quickly restore the practical skills missed by students.

During the anti-epidemic regime-restricted measures from 2019 to 2022 students scientific group (SSG) of disaster medicine organized sixty meetings. During 2019-2020 there were nine meetings; during 2020-2021 - thirteen meetings; during 2021-2022 - thirty eight meetings. Over the past 3 academic years there were thirty nine meetings about cardiopulmonary resuscitation. In the 2019-2020 academic year seven

meetings were held on cardiopulmonary resuscitation; in the 2020-2021 year - ten; in the 2021-2022 there were twenty seven meetings. The overall amount of people who visited the meetings of the student scientific group of disaster medicine was 735 people, whereas 326 people were participating in the meetings about cardiopulmonary resuscitation. The peak of attendance of these meetings was in the 2021-2022 where there were 200 people at the conference because at that period of time the student scientific group could invite students for offline practice. In the 2019-2020 year there were 100 participants in this kind of meetings. The smallest amount of people who took part in the meetings were in the 2020-2021 year where there were only 26 people. This happened because of the spreading of the coronavirus infectious and the change in the format of the meetings to the distant one. During the distance conferences there were such themes: ensuring the safety of medical workers when working with victims and patients; studying the usage of the personal protective equipment; changes in the algorithm of the first aid and basic cardiopulmonary resuscitation.

The studying of the algorithm of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation is realized by the theoretical and practical meetings. The main goal in the theoretical meetings was in the detailed analysis of the algorithm of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation. During the distant theoretical meetings participants were studying the difference and peculiarities of the algorithm of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation, which was recommended during the pandemic of the coronavirus infection in 2022; the differences between algorithms 2021 year from 2015 year; the detailed study of the accreditation algorithm of cardiopulmonary resuscitation for the exam to work as a nurse and for exams as part of the

intermediate certification. Also, in the theoretical meetings there was an analysis of the rules of usage the automated external defibrillator during the cardiopulmonary resuscitation during the first aid. It is important to note that the special attention in the organization of theoretical meetings is given to the study of the rules of one's own safety and safety of the medical staff and patients when providing first aid to victims at the pre-hospital stage. With the onset of the pandemic there is an increased need in such type of the meetings.

The aim of the practical offline meetings was the practice of technique of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation with the usage of the simulation equipment with feedback. From 2019 to 2022 years among all meetings there were 38,5% theoretical meetings and 61,5% practical. The percent of the meetings about cardiopulmonary resuscitation is nearly equal in each year and it is

about 75,25% from all meetings during the academic year. However, the ratio between theoretical and practical meetings is different each year. In the 2019-2020 there were more practical meetings (85,7%) than theoretical (14,3%). In the 2020-2021 academic year due to the spread of the coronavirus infectious and introduction of the distance learning format of education the amount of the practical meetings was cut off and became equal to the amount of the theoretical meetings - 50%. In the 2021-2022 academic year the amount of the meetings where there was the theoretical studying of the algorithm of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation (51,8%) was a bit higher than the amount of the practical meetings (48,2%) (picture 2).

Picture 2. The graph of the amount of different types of the meetings from 2019 to 2022 years

When the possibility of conducting in-person practical CPR classes in small groups during the pandemic emerged, the question arose about ensuring the safety of students when working with simulation equipment. Special treatment of mannequin with antiseptic compositions was carried out after the class, the algo-

rithm of basic CPR without artificial ventilation, recommended by ERC and National Resuscitation Council for the period of COVID-19 spread, as well as teaching students to perform CPR using Ambu bag, was used during the training. To increase the productivity of practical training, an algorithm consisting of several stages was developed (Table 1).

Table 1

Algorithm for simulation training of basic CPR

Stages of training	Learning a practical skill	Aim of the stage
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ assessment of students' knowledge of the algorithm of cardiopulmonary resuscitation ○ task – to assist the injured within the framework of their knowledge and skills 	Identification and analysis of mistakes, increasing the effectiveness of training in following stages of the parse algorithm of cardiopulmonary resuscitation.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ studying the current updated algorithm according to the European and National Resuscitation Council (2021); ○ detailed study of the algorithm necessary for demonstration at the practical part of the accreditation. ○ Repetition of the sequence of actions of the algorithms ○ Review exam requirements ○ Demonstration of cardiopulmonary resuscitation by the head of the student scientific group or student tutor. 	Studying and repeating the theoretical aspects of the cardiopulmonary resuscitation algorithm
3	students practicing the algorithm of cardiopulmonary resuscitation on an interactive mannequin under the supervision of the head of the student scientific group and the student tutor, who, if necessary, helped to analyze and correct the mistakes they made	Practicing the algorithm of cardiopulmonary resuscitation

At the first stage there were 75,12% of students who did the cardiopulmonary resuscitation right and the number of mistakes made was 8. The most frequent errors were in diagnosing the patient's breathing (38.1%), in calling an ambulance, and also in performing chest compressions due to failure to observe the compression point (23.8%). Incorrect hand positioning resulted in an inability to achieve adequate depth of compression in 75.2% of students and adequate frequency in 37.1%. Excessive frequency of chest compressions (more than 120 per minute) was observed in 86%. The identified errors were the most typical for students with a deficit of practice during the pandemic [1, 4, 5, 10]. Nevertheless, the given practice algorithm allowed the majority of students to correct their mistakes by the end of the class. After repeating the theory and several repetitions (3 to 5) of algorithm in practice completely on a simulation simulator with feedback, the correctness of the CPR algorithm increased to 93.8% compared to the first stage, and the number of mistakes made decreased to an average of 2. Repeated attendance at the practical session on the same topic allowed the students to form a solid practical skill.

A study of student attendance at additional group meetings showed that the established practical skills platform was the most in demand among fourth- and fifth-year students before their accreditation exams for admission to the nursing profession. Despite the opportunity to learn new aspects of their chosen field and to hone their skills learned in theory in practice, most students preferred to get into the new tendency of obtaining information remotely.

Conclusion: Analysis of the work of the student scientific group showed the possibilities of training students not only in the field of basic scientific activities, theoretical and practical knowledge and skills in the field of disaster medicine, but also the relevance as a

platform to fill the lack of practical skills during the pandemic. Attendance varied depending on the waves of anti-epidemic regime-restrictive measures and the schedule of accreditation examinations. Unfortunately, we have to point out the limitation of the capacity of simulation practical lessons within the student scientific group, the need for pre-registration, as increasing the group for a practical lesson more than 10-15 participants led to a decrease in individual efficiency of practical skills training, more repetitions were required. Another significant point is to continue to maintain the practical skill of basic CPR in students and retraining when the resuscitation algorithm changes, returning to the traditional performance of CPR.

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EMERGENCY HELP IN THE PSYCHIATRIC PRACTICE OF INTERN DOCTORS

Rusina S.,

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Nervous Diseases, Psychiatry and Medical Psychology. of S.M. Savenko Higher educational institution of Ukraine "Bukovynian State Medical University",

Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Nikoryak R.

Aspirant of the National Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education of Shupyk, Kyiv, Ukraine

ABSTRACT

In the period of training in the internship of the first and, especially, the second year of training, close attention should be paid, along with theoretical knowledge, to practical skills and abilities in preparing doctors for professional professional work with mentally ill patients. It is important in this direction to provide qualified and timely emergency care to the patient, on which the life and health of both him and the people around him depend.

Keywords: interns, mental patients, emergency care.

Formulation of the problem.

The modern information society and the growing prevalence of diseases, in particular, mental diseases, make high demands on the professional training of future specialists in the field of psychiatry. The development of a strategy to improve the mental health of Ukrainians, especially during times of war, is an integral part of the work of higher educational medical institutions of Ukraine to train medical personnel aimed at a positive shift in the timely diagnosis, treatment and prevention of psychopathological disorders.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Serious challenges of society, provoked by various socio-political (threat of the third world), epidemiological (COVID) and medical-psychological (military operations) reasons, encourage the reform of higher education in Ukraine with the aim of improving the training of professional medical workers. Socially stressful

factors have led to the fact that mental disorders have become the most common today. Therefore, it is important to introduce emergency care standards into the educational process, which ensure early diagnosis of mental disorders, sometimes in combination with physical ones, and timely provision of emergency care in order to preserve the health of the nation (5).

In medical practice, psychopathological conditions that require immediate medical intervention with suddenly occurring aggressive, auto-aggressive, destructive and other dangerous actions of the patient are quite often observed. Medical intervention, including for these patients, is understood as a complex of organizational, pharmacotherapeutic, psychotherapeutic and legal measures of a medical nature (1).

Such exacerbations are most often manifested by psychomotor agitation, which is accompanied by de-